

Growth Performance, Carcass Characteristics and Histological Indices of White Fulani (Bunaji) Bull Yearling Calves Fed Graded Levels of Urea and Molasses Ensiled Rice Straw Supplemented with Maize Offal and Cowpea Husk

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Abstract

The study was carried out at Duware farm along Yola-Fufore Road Adamawa state. ix yearling white Fulani (Bunaji) bull calves weighed 80kg-100kg were fed graded levels of urea and molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with maize offal and cowpea husk to investigate the growth performance, carcass characteristics and histological indices. The treatments diets consist of graded levels of urea and molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with maize offal for T₁, graded levels of urea and molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with cowpea husk in T₂, and graded levels of urea and molasses ensiled rice straw only in T₃ (control group). The feeds were offered at 8; 00 am in the morning and 6:00 pm in the evening, remnants were weight before fresh feeds were offered, mineral lick and water was provided ad-libitum, and animals were weight weekly to determine their growth performance. Two weeks adaptation period was carried out, the experiment last for three months including the adaptation period, statistical package for data analysis was completely randomize design (CRD) and the values were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) means were separated using least significant difference (LSD).

Keywords: *white Fulani (Bunaji) bull, treatments diets, feed, growth performance.*

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Introduction

In Nigeria, the populace is predominantly marked by inadequate protein intake both in quality and quantity Niania et al (2021). Low level of protein intake in Nigeria is due to low level of livestock productivity and high cost of animal protein Saidu et al (2021). The most populous and widely distributed breeds of cattle in Nigeria have been found to be the white Fulani cattle pastoralist controlling more than 95% of the national herd and has been the major source of domestic meat and milk supply; many of which are reared under the transhumance farming system while a few belongs to institution and private farms (Dim et al 2012). The contribution of livestock to the livelihoods of the developing communities and the entire world requires enhanced understanding of livestock numerous and compound roles played, as their contribution to the dietary status of the world population is well recognized in term of food (protein) from animal origin, products and byproducts. Saidu et al (2021). The performance of animal fed crop residues is limited by poor intake, low nitrogen contents and poor digestibility Amudu and Okunlola (2020). Feed scarcity has been the major limiting factor in improving livestock productivity (Naik et al., 2013).

Material and Methods

Study Area

The research was carried out at Duware farm along Yola-Fufore Road Adamawa state. Nigeria, situated within the savannah region and lies between latitude 9° , 14° N and longitude 12° 21° with an altitude of about 152m above sea level. The state has tropical climate with distinct dry and wet seasons. The rainfall begins in April and ends in late October, while the dry season commence in late October or November and ends in April. It has an average minimum and maximum temperature of 18 & 40°C and relative humidity of 20 and 80%. Adamawa state has an international boundary with the Cameroon Republic along its eastern boarder (Adebayo and Tukur 1999). Adamawa shares boundaries with Taraba State to the south and west, Gombe State to the North-west and Borno State to the north.

Experimental Animals

Six calves aged between 12-15 months were used, weighing 80kg-100kg. The calves were weighed to obtain their initial weight at arrival and treated for both internal and external parasites and subjected to pre-experimental adaptation for two weeks, with three dietary treatments. The feeds were mixed and fed as complete ration daily at 8:00 am and 6:00 pm, housed under a simple shed made of a woods and thatches to prevent harsh weather conditions,

Experimental Design

A completely randomize design (CRD) was used to carried out the research, and the values was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and means were separated using least significant difference (LSD).

Procurement and Processing of Experimental Diets

The rice straw was procured from local farmers in Jimeta-Yola in Adamawa state; dried, cut into 10 cm particle size and stored in bags for easy packaging in the silos for ensiling.

T₁. 4kg of urea, 5 kg of molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with maize offal

T₂. 4kg of urea, 5 kg of molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with cowpea husk

T₂. 4kg of urea, 5 kg of molasses ensiled rice straw only (control group)

4kg of urea and 5 kg of molasses was dissolved in 100 liters of water and 100kg of rice straw was submerged into the solution, pressed and tied in an air tight polythene silos bag for air exclusion, knotted

to achieve anaerobic condition for 21 days for better urea hydrolysis as documented by Adamu *et al* (2016) who opined that once the oxygen is exhausted, only anaerobic organism can survive, this allowed the growth of acid forming and photolytic bacteria which convert carbohydrate into lactic acid, protein into ammonia, amines and amino acid which caused decreased pH in the ensiled materials which kills both yeast and mould, acidity continue to increase to a level where the acid producing organisms themselves are killed, at this pH and time ensiling is completed.

Chemical Analysis

The chemical composition of the feed sample was determined in the laboratory; the analysis was conducted to determine Nitrogen (N) for crude protein (CP), crude fibre, ether extract, nitrogen free extract (NFE) and ash content using the proximate analysis (AOAC, 2004) procedure. Acid and neutral detergent fibre were determined according to the procedure described by (Van Soest *et al.*, 1991).

Data Collection

Dry matter intake (DMI)

Feed intake was determined by collecting and weighing the amount of remnant (leftover) every morning before feeding fresh feeds and subtracting the leftover from the total amount of feed offered. Feed intake was determined using the formula below:

$$\text{Feed intake} = \text{feed given} - \text{left over} \quad (1)$$

Live weight gain

Live weight was measured according to Nyako *et al.*, (2015) procedure. The animals were weighed on arrival (at the beginning) for initial weight and subsequently on weekly intervals individually using weighing tape/band which were recorded. The differences between the previous weeks and the current week gave changes in live weight. Daily weight gain was obtained by dividing the total weight gain by the number of days of the feeding trial as described by (Gabdo *et al.*, 2016).

Feed conversion ratio (FCR)

Feed conversion ratio was obtained by dividing daily dry matter intake (DMI) by average daily live weight gain, feed conversion ratio was determined using the formula:

$$\text{Feed conversion ratio} = \frac{\text{Total dry mater intake (kg)}}{\text{Total weight gain (kg)}} \quad (2)$$

Digestibility study

Digestibility study commenced after the end of the feeding trial, the animals were randomly selected and confined in an improvised local metabolic cages/crate for 14 days adjustment period to get used to the new environment (metabolic crate), prior to (7) days faecal collection period. They were fitted with collection bags to facilitate faecal collection using a polythene bags, one calf from each treatment, the animals were fed their respective treatment diets. Total faecal outputs were collected daily, weighed and 10% sub-samples were taken and oven dried at 60 to 65^oC for 24 hours as described by (Nyako *et al.*, 2015). The faeces were dried, weight and then ground using pestle and mortar and stored before chemical analysis as described by (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2016).

Nutrients digestibility (ND) was determined by the formula as described by Adamu et al. (2015).

$$ND = \frac{\text{Nutrient intake} - \text{Nutrients in faeces}}{\text{Nutrient intake}} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

Dry matter (DM)

The dry matter content was determined by oven drying at 105°C for 3 hours until constant weight was obtained (AOAC, 2004).

Crude protein, nitrogen free extracts and ether extract

Crude protein (CP), Nitrogen free extract (NFE) and Ether extract (EE) were determined using the official method of Analysis of the Association of Official Analytical Chemist. (AOAC 2004) crude fibre was determined using the trichloro acetic acid digestion method.

Acid detergent fibre (ADF) and neutral detergent Fibre (NDF)

Van Soest *et al.* (1991) methods as reported by (DeBoever *et al.*, 2002) was used to determined acid detergent fiber (ADF) and neutral detergent fibre (NDF)

Total Ash (TA) and Mineral (Ca, P and K)

Total Ash (AS) was determined by muffle furnace at 500°C to 600°C for four hours while mineral content were determined using Microwave accelerated reaction system (MARS) emission spectrographic procedure.

Results

Table 1. Gross and Calculated Chemical Composition of Experimental Treated (Ensiled) and Untreated Rice Straw (%DM basis)

Nutrients	DM	CP	CF	EE	Ash	NFE	NDF	ADF
Rice straw	92.40	9.0	10.0	2.1	1.2	68.70	11.38	3.47
Ensiled rice straw	98.5	12.2	4.0	2.4	10.0	80.4	29.11	13.53
Nutrients	MO	OM	Cel	Hem	Lig	Ca	P	
Rice straw	4.93	93.50	3.33	7.91	0.14	0.45	0.43	
Ensiled rice straw	18.20	79.36	12.98	15.58	0.55	0.51	0.47	

Note: Dry mater (DM); Crude protein (CP); Crude fibre (CF); Ether extract (EE); Ash; Nitrogen free extract (NFE); Neutral Detergent Fibre (NDF); Acid Detergent Fibre (ADF); Moisture (MO); Organic Matter (OM); Cellulose (Cel); Hemi cellulose (Hem); Lignin (Lig).; Metabolizable Energy = ME (Kcal/kg) = (37 x %CP + 81.1 x %EE + 35.5 x %N.F.E NFE = 100 – (%MO + %EE + % CP + % CF%+ ASH). Organic Matter (OM) = Dry mater (DM) – Total Ash (TA). Metabolizable energy (Kcal/kg) 2,998.37

Table 2. Gross and Calculated Chemical Composition of Experimental Maize Offal (% DM basis)

Nutrients	MO	DM	CP	EE	CF	Ash	OM
Maize offal	3.50	86.10	10.52	1.30	10.85	4.00	81.00
Nutrients	NFE	ADF	NDF	Cel	Hem	Lig	
Maize offal	55.51	20.45	20.35	5.12	2.5	1.85	

Note: Moisture (MO); Dry mater (DM); Crude protein (CP); Ether extract (EE); Crude fibre (CF); Ash; Organic Matter (OM); Nitrogen free extract (NFE); Acid Detergent Fibre (ADF); Neutral Detergent Fibre (NDF); Cellulose (Cel); Hemi cellulose (Hem); Lignin (Lig).; Metabolizable Energy = ME (Kcal/kg) = (37 x %CP + 81.1 x %EE + 35.5 x %N.F.E NFE = 100 - (%MO + %EE + % CP + % CF%+ ASH). Organic Matter (OM) = Dry mater (DM) - Total Ash (TA). Metabolizable energy (Kcal/kg) 2,998.37

Table 3. Gross and Calculated Chemical Composition of Experimental Cowpea Husks (% DM basis)

Nutrients (%)	DM	CP	CF	EE	Ash	NFE	NDF	ADF
Cowpea Husk	88.50	3.5	9.0	1.0	1.1	76.0	66.1	39.3

Note: Dry mater (DM); Crude protein (CP); Crude fibre (CF); Ether Extract (EE); Ash; Nitrogen Free Extract (NFE); Neutral Detergent fiber (NDF); Acid detergent fiber (ADF).

Table 4. Growth Performance of White Fulani (Bunaji) Bull Yearling Calves Fed Treated (ensiled) and Untreated Rice Straw Supplemented with Energy Sources (maize offal and cowpea husk)

Parameter	T1 ERS/MO	T2 ERS/CH	T3 ERS	SEM	LSD
Final body weight (kg)	107.99 ^a	104.90 ^b	99.80 ^c	0.03	0.13*
Total weight gain (kg)	37.54 ^a	34.47 ^b	29.39 ^c	0.01	0.03*
ADWG (g/a/day)	425.98 ^a	388.95 ^b	329.78 ^c	0.01	0.03*
Dry matter intake (kg/a/day)					
Total dry matter intake (kg)	419.98 ^a	417.90 ^b	401.89 ^d	0.03	0.13*
Ensiled rice straw(kg)	318.99 ^a	313.89 ^b	305.98 ^d	0.03	0.11*
Energy supplements (kg)	104.87 ^a	102.59 ^b	101.98 ^d	0.03	0.11*
ADFI (kg/a/day)	4.68 ^a	4.59 ^{ab}	4.44 ^b	0.03	0.12 ^{ns}
Feed conversion ratio	11.19 ^d	12.12 ^c	13.67 ^b	0.03	0.08*

Note: Mean on the same row bearing different superscript differ significantly (P<0.05) *, SEM=Standard Error Mean, LSD=Least significant different, NS=No significant different, ADFI=Average daily feed intake, ADWG=Average daily weight gain, Energy supplements, Treated (Ensiled) rice straw and maize offal).

Growth Performance of White Fulani (Bunaji) Bull Yearling Calves Fed Treated (ensiled) and Untreated Rice Straw Supplemented with Energy Sources (maize offal and cowpea husk)

The result is presented in Table 4. The final body weight (FBW kg), total weight gain (TWG kg) and average daily weight gain (ADWG g/day) indicated significant (P<0.05) difference across the treatments, the final body weight ranged from 99.80 to 107.99kg. The highest value 107.99kg was recorded in T₁, followed by 104.90kg in T₂ and the least value 99.80kg was recorded in T₃ The Total weight gain (TWG kg) ranged from 29.39 to 37.54kg. The highest values was recorded in T₁ with 37.54kg followed by 34.47kg

in T₂, 29.39 kg in T₃ as the least recorded values. The average daily weight gain ranged from 329.78 to 425.98 g/a/day, the highest values was recorded in T₁ with 425.98kg/a/day followed by T₂ with 388.95 kg/a/day, T₃ with 329.78 kg/a/day as the least values was recorded.

The total dry matter intake (DMI), ensiled rice (kg), energy supplement (kg) and average daily feed intake (kg/a/day) showed significant (P<0.05) different across the treatments. The total dry matter intake (DMI) ranged from 401.89 to 419.98 kg recorded. The highest dry matter intake recorded in T₁ with 419.98 kg followed by T₂ with 417.90 kg and the least was recorded in T₃ with 401.89 kg. Ensiled rice straw (kg) ranged from 305.98 to 318.99kg recorded. The least value 305.98kg was recorded in T₃, 313.89kg in T₂ and the highest values 318.99kg was recorded in T₁. Energy supplement ranged from 101.98 to 104.87kg recorded. The highest value 104.87kg was recorded in T₁, followed by 102.59kg in T₂ and the least value 101.98 kg was recorded in T₃. The average daily feed intake (ADFI) ranged from 4.44 to 4.68 kg/a/day recorded. The highest daily feed intake was recorded in T₁ with 4.68 kg/a/day, followed by T₂ with 4.59 kg/a/day as the least value recorded in T₃ with 4.44 kg/a/day. The feed conversion ratio (FCR) showed significant (P<0.05) different across the treatments. The FCR ranged from 11.19 to 13.67, The highest value 13.67. The highest value was recorded in T₂ with 13.67 and the least value was recorded in T₁ with 11.19.

Effect of Carcass Characteristics of White Fulani (Bunaji) Bull Yearling Calves Fed Treated (ensiled) and Untreated Rice Straw Supplemented with Energy Sources (maize offal and cowpea husk)

Results on the absolute weights, carcass characteristics and internal organs of experimental Yearling white (Fulani Bunaji) bull calves fed urea and molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with energy sources is presented in Tables 5.

Table 5. Effects of Carcass Characteristics of White Fulani (Bunaji) Bull Yearling Calves Fed Treated (ensiled) and Untreated Rice Straw Supplemented with Energy Sources (maize offal and cowpea husk)

Parameters	T ₁ (ERS & MO)	T ₂ (ERS & CH)	T ₃ (ERS Only)	SEM
Primal Cuts				
Rump (kg)	2.79 ^a	2.47 ^a	2.02 ^a	9.26
Hind shank (kg)	14.69 ^a	14.53 ^{ab}	13.67 ^b	14.92
Loin (kg)	1.19 ^a	1.13 ^{ab}	1.00 ^b	8.23
Organs				
Liver (kg)	1.49 ^a	1.37 ^{ab}	1.22 ^b	0.14
Spleen (kg)	1.00 ^a	0.98 ^a	0.79 ^a	0.03
Kidney (kg)	0.75 ^a	0.65 ^{ab}	0.50 ^b	7.04

Note: ERS=Ensiled rice straw, MO=Maize offal, CH=Cowpea husk.

Primal Cuts

Rump weight (DW) (kg)

Rump of experimental bull calves fed urea and molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with energy sources presented in Table 5, revealed no significant (P>0.05) difference among the experimental treatments groups, differences in values among treatment means were only numerical. The SEM value for this parameter was 9.26.

Hind shank weight (kg)

Results on the hind shank weight performance of bull calves fed urea and molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with energy sources presented in Table 5 revealed a significant ($P < 0.05$) difference on the weight between treatments means in this experiment. SEM was 14.92 for this parameter.

Loin weight (kg)

Table 5 showed results on loin weight performance of experimental bull calves fed urea and molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with energy sources revealed significance ($P > 0.05$) difference between the experimental treatment means. The SEM for the parameter was 8.23.

Organs/Offal Weight

Liver weight (LW) (kg)

Results on liver weight performance of experimental bull calves administered urea and molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with energy sources presented in Table 5 revealed that liver weight means was highest (1.49) in T_1 , 1.37 in T_2 , and 1.22 in T_3 (control treatment) significance ($P < 0.05$) difference was observed among all the treatments means. SEM value for this parameter was 0.14.

Spleen weight (kg)

Spleen weight performance of experimental bull calves administered urea and molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with energy sources presented in Table 5 revealed spleen weight was highest in T_1 1.00 with a progressive decline in spleen weight trend to 0.98 in T_2 and 0.79 T_3 among all the treatments means including the control. SEM value in this parameter was 0.03.

Kidney weight (kg)

Results on the Kidney weight performance of experimental bull calves administered urea and molasses ensiled rice straw supplemented with energy sources presented in Table 5. The results revealed that kidney values among all the treatments means were significantly ($P > 0.05$) difference. The highest values were 0.75 in T_1 , 0.65 in T_2 and 0.50 in T_3 the control. SEM values for this parameter were 7.04.

Effect of Histopathology of White Fulani (Bunaji) Bull Yearling Calves Fed Treated (ensiled) and Untreated Rice Straw Supplemented with Energy Sources (maize offal and cowpea husk)

Histopathology of the Liver

Liver histological interpretations in all the treatments groups revealed significant orientation of the cells (hepatocyte) and regular sinusoidal placement with perfect cellular permeated evident inside the sinusoid, T_1 , and T_2 while T_3 Control group revealed normal orientation of hepatocyte and mitotic cells, no pathological effect on the tissue of the liver despite urea and molasses inclusion levels in all the treatments including the control (CV) H&E x200.

Histopathology of the spleen

Photomicrograph results of the spleen revealed no congestion in areas with red pulp, normal white pulp and several phagocytic cells in T_1 and T_2 . Constricted hyperemic region of the blood vessels are seen in T_3 and the results confirmed no clear regions of the red pulp, although highly scattered phagocytic cells in white pulp, no signs of unusual orientation of pathological effects between all the treatments including the control as displayed. H&E x200.

Histopathology of the kidney

Histopathological kidney results in T_1 indicated usual glomerular structure with normal straight collecting ducts and convoluted collecting ducts T_1 , T_2 and T_3 Photomicrograph section of the kidney displayed normal morphological arrangement of medullary section.

Discussion

Proximate Composition of Maize Offal

The chemical composition of maize offal is presented in Table 1. The compositional dry matter recorded value (86.10%) of maize offal was consistent with the value of 86.01% as revealed by (Ahmed *et al.*, 2011). The dry matter of maize offal was 86.10% lower than the value of 89.21% reported by Ashiru *et al.* (2013). The crude protein (CP) values 10.52% in this study falls within the values of 9-14% as reported by Aduku, (2005) as the minimum nutrient requirement for small ruminants. The crude protein values obtained were lower than the value of 11.90% reported by Abdullahi *et al.* (2016) who fed urea treated sorghum chaff as a basal diets supplemented with maize offal's to Yankasa rams. The crude protein of maize offal (10.52%) reduced significant due to the time / age of maturity as reported by (Shyama *et al.*, 2016). The recorded 10.52% values were lower than the value of 13.6% as reported by (Naik *et al.*, 2014) who fed hydroponic maize to lactating cows. However, increased in crude protein content in treated hydroponic maize might be attributed to the loss in dry matter (DM), particularly carbohydrate, through respiration (oxidation) during germination.

The ether extract (EE) of maize offal (1.30%) was consistent with 1.40% reported by (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2016) who fed urea treated sorghum chaff as a basal diets supplemented with maize offal's to Yankasa rams.

The crude fibre (CF) content of maize offal was 10.85% figures values was lower than the values 11.85% reported by (Alikwe *et al.*, 2012) who fed maize bran, wheat offal and rice bran to West African Dwarf goats. The nitrogen free extract (NFE) of maize offal recorded was 55.51% lower than the value of 82.12 to 84.15% as reported by (Naik *et al.*, 2012); this might be attributed to the increase in the number and size of cell walls for the synthesis of structural carbohydrate. Although higher than the values 32.4% as revealed by Abdullahi *et al.* (2016) who fed urea treated sorghum chaff as a basal diets supplemented with maize offal's to Yankasa rams, and also higher than the figure 50.75% reported by (Gabdo *et al.*, 2016) who Offered *Leptadenia Hastata* as a Basal Diet.

The total Ash value 4.00% maize offal was higher than dry maize seed 1.57% as reported by (Morsy *et al.*, 2013). However, the recorded value (4.00%) was lower than the figure of 9.36% as reported by (Naik *et al.*, 2016). The total ash content was lower than the values of 7.85% as reported by (Ashiru *et al.*, 2013). The recorded value of maize offal 4.00% was higher than the value 3.69% as reported by (Babale *et al.*, 2018) who fed Maize Cob Replacing Maize Bran with Cowpea Husk Basal Diet to red Sokoto Goat. The higher value might be attributed to the increase cell walls for the synthesis of structural carbohydrate.

Growth Performance of Yearling White Fulani (Bunaji) Bull Calves Fed Ensiled Rice Straw Supplemented with Energy Sources

Dry Matter Intake

The results of dry matter intake (kg) of the diets of yearling bull calves fed ensiled rice supplemented with energy sources were shown in Table 4. The figures (401.89 to 419.98) were higher than the findings of Jasmine *et al.* (2019) who recorded (166.26 to 169.40kg) of dry matter intake when the authors fed hydroponic maize to cross bred calves. The high values might have been attributed to the composition of the diets which were adequate to meet the protein requirements (16-20%) of calves and also effective rumen function as reported by Donna *et al.* (2006) who fed and managed baby calves from three month of age. ADF and NDF 25 to 28% of the animal for proper rumen function, maintenance of normal pH 6.2 to 6.8, saliva production and maintenance of rumen mat as recommended by NRC (2000).

Ensiled rice straw 305.98 to 318.99 obtained in the present study were lower than the values (391.13 to 431.79kg) as reported by (Sekhonyana *et al.*, 2015) who fed urea treated maize Stover on the growth performance of cross bred heifers calves. Also, the recorded values (305.98 to 318.99kg) were higher than

the figures (167.07 to 197.17 kg) reported by Rajkumar *et al.* (2018) who fed hydroponic maize as a partial feed substitute in the ration of crossbred calves. The higher values in the present study could be due to the energy and protein constituents of the ensiled rice straw, tenderness, lushness and its succulent nature.

Live Weight Gain

The total weight gain (TWG) and average daily weight gain (ADWG) of yearling bull calves fed ensiled rice straw supplemented with energy sources showed significant ($P > 0.05$) difference across the treatments means (Table 4). The total weight gain ranged from 29.39 to 37.54 kg in this study were lower than the value of 53.17 to 62.67 kg reported by (Sekhonyana *et al.*, 2015) who fed maize Stover treated with urea to cross bred heifer calves. The highest total weight gain was recorded in T₁ (37.54 kg) and the least value (29.39 kg) was obtained in T₃. The increase intake could be as a result of supplementation of the energy and an accompanying improvement in the utilization of non-protein nitrogen in the treated straw which resulted in an improvement in the live weight gain of the animals. Similarly, the highest weight gains in T₁ correspond with higher dry matter and nutrient intake as reported by (Dawit *et al.*, 2013) who determined the growth performance of Jersey calves fed maize Stover silage based total mixed ration compared to calves fed hay and concentrate separately. The figures (29.39 to 37.54 kg) were lower than the figures (30.39 to 40.58 kg) revealed by Rajkumar *et al.* (2018) who fed hydroponic maize as partial substitute in the ration of cross bred calves. The lower values recorded might be attributed to many factors including particle size, chewing frequency and effectiveness as well as rate of fermentation of the potentially digestible NDF, the lower value could be attributed to differences in the initial average body weight of the animals, and also the growth performance of animals is directly related to the protein and energy obtained from a given ration as reported by Dawit *et al.* (2013) who fed a basal diet of maize offal to crossbred heifer calves. Live weight gain depends on several factors such as breed characteristics, age, initial live weight, plane of nutrition and management practice as opined by Fazaeli *et al.* (2011).

Feed Conversion Ratio

Feed conversion ratio of yearling bull calves fed ensiled rice straw supplemented with energy sources showed significant ($P < 0.05$) difference across the treatment groups as presented in Table 4. Feed conversion ratio measured the efficiency of bull calves to convert feed consumed in to meat; thus, the lower the value, the better the feed conversion ratio (Adebisi *et al.*, 2018). Feed conversion ratio ranged from 11.19 to 13.67; the highest value of 13.67 was recorded in T₃, the best and lowest figure 11.19 was recorded in T₁. The figures 11.19 to 13.67 were however much higher than the values of 4.7 to 5.5 as reported by (Dawit *et al.*, 2013). This observation might have been attributed to the presence of nutrients solution which enhanced the crude protein contents of the hydroponic leading to the uptake of nitrogenous compounds. This finding coincides with (Dung *et al.*, 2010) who reported on nutrient contents and *in-sacco* digestibility of barley grain and sprouted barley.

Carcass Characteristics and Internal Organs Indices of Yearling White Fulani (Bunaji) Bull Calves Fed Ensiled Rice Straw Supplemented with Energy Sources

Primal cuts (kg)

Rump (kg)

Rump weight indicated no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference across the treatments. The weight value recorded in this study were 2.02 to 2.79 and lower than 9.50 to 11.00% of shoulder as reported by (Ayandiran *et al.* 2019) during blood metabolites and carcass characteristics of west African dwarf goat fed bread waste and moringa oleifera leaf, 40.56 to 43.28% as submitted by (Odeomelan *et al.* 2014) were also higher than the figures obtained in the present study.

Hind Shank (kg)

Significant ($P < 0.05$) differences were observed on dietary treatments. The values 13.67 to 14.69 were higher than the figures 8.50 to 8.86% as reported by (Ayandiran *et al* 2020) submitted on carcass quality of west African dwarf goat fed shear butter nut meal. 7.76 to 8.98% of goat forelimb as reported by Ayandiran *et al* 2020 the authors evaluated carcass quality of west African dwarf goat fed shear butter nut meal, the cut parts values of animals depend on how adequate the animals were able to utilize nutrients in feed to synthesize body tissues (Okay *et al* 2014).

Loin (kg)

Loin weight revealed significance ($P < 0.05$) difference among the treatment means. However, observed mean values of 1.00-1.19 in this trial was lower than the figures of 7.41-8.07% submitted by (Ayandiran *et al* 2020) which are comparable to 8.05-13.15 as obtained by (Okay *et al* 2014) although lower values were reported by (Ukpabi *et al* 2007) on the evaluation of muuna seed meal based diets for goat production.

Organs / Offal

Liver (kg)

Significant ($P < 0.05$) difference was observed among the treatment groups, the liver values 1.22-1.49 fall within the values 1.98-2.19 been the submission of (Ayandiran *et al* 2020). 2.92-5.29% as reported by (Ayandiran *et al* 2019) on blood metabolites and carcass characteristics of West African goat fed bread waste and moringa oleifera leaf.

Spleen (kg)

Spleen weight of 0.79-1.00 showed no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference, only numerical values differences were observed across the treatment means, the 0.17-0.28 was recorded by (Ayandiran *et al* 2020) on carcass quality of west African dwarf goat fed shear butter nut meal and 0.61-1.40 as reported by (Ayandiran *et al* 2019) on blood metabolites and carcass characteristics of west African goat fed bread waste and moringa oleifera leaf. Kidney weight ranged from 0.50-0.75, significance difference ($P < 0.05$) was reported to exist between kidney weights in the treatment means. These are within the ranged research findings of (Ayandiran *et al* 2020) who reported 0.49-0.50 on carcass quality of west African dwarf goat fed shear butter nut meal but contradicted the values 1.09-1.26 as reported by (Ayandiran *et al* 2019) on blood metabolites and carcass characteristics of west African goat fed bread waste and moringa oleifera leaf. Ensiled rice straw enhanced flesh deposition in the carcass and impacted no visible abnormalities on the visceral organs.

Histopathological Indices of Yearling White Fulani (Bunaji) Bull Calves Fed Ensiled Rice Straw Supplemented with Energy Sources

Histopathology of the Liver

Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) exist with sinusoidal congestion, hyperplasia and widened focal area of hepatic necrosis, the liver displayed presence of hepatic necrosis in liver tissue in this study, which falls within the report of Agboola *et al* (2018) on the influence of sodium acetate, sodium propionate and their combination on nutrients digestibility and blood profile obtained from healthy bird at slaughter, which indirectly affected the liver when the author investigate nutrients digestibility and blood profile of broiler chicken reared under high temperature

Spleen (kg)

Significant ($P < 0.05$) differences were observed across the dietary treatments. The histopathological investigation of Yearling white Fulani (Bunaji) bull calves fed ensiled rice straw supplemented with energy

sources in the spleen in this trial revealed dissociation of hepatic cords, widening of sinusoidal spaces and severe congestion with mild presence of neutrophils which coincide with the submission of Agboola *et al* (2018) when the authors evaluate growth performance and Gut histomorphology of broiler starter.

Histopathology of the Kidney

The distortion of the histology readily observed in kidney revealed significant differences ($P < 0.05$) ranged from moderate to severe hepatocellular degeneration and necrosis of hepatocyte and severe inflammatory cells. as reported by Oladipo *et al* (2019). Kidney showed striated muscles, degeneration and multifocal coagulation necrosis of tabular epithelium as reported by Oladipo *et al* (2019).

Conclusion

The growth performance revealed highest final body weight, total weight gain, average daily weight gain and total dry matter intake was recorded in T1 fed (Ensiled rice straw supplemented with maize offal) and the lowest feed conversion ratio was recorded in the same treatment group. The effects of carcass characteristics on primal cuts (Rump, hind shank, and loin) and organs (Liver, spleen and kidney) highest values were also recorded in T1. Histopathological indices of liver revealed sinusoidal congestion, hyperplasia and widened focal area of hepatic necrosis in liver tissue, the spleen in this trial revealed dissociation of hepatic cords, widening of sinusoidal spaces and severe congestion with mild presence of neutrophils, while the kidney revealed moderate to severe hepatocellular degeneration and necrosis of hepatocyte and severe inflammatory cells. The results of this studies recommended the feeding of ensiled rice straw supplemented with maize offal due to the highest growth performance and carcass characteristics in Bunaji calves.

Other studies should be conducted to determine the deleterious effects of urea on Bunaji Yearling calves/cattle.

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